

On the Way to Microservice: Exploring Problems and Solutions from Online Q&A Community

TABLE I: Solution Strategies for Microservices in Software Development Process.

Phase	Category	Problem	Solution Strategy	Example id	
AD (11.25%)	Microservice Design (11.25%)	Design Strategy	Decentralizing application : ① by scale [1], ② by domain [2]	answer [3], [4]	
			Designing database architecture by [5]: ① Approach with shared database, ② Approach with domain-based database	answer [6], [7]	
			Organizing microservice teams [8]: ① CI/CD ② Automated Testing	answer [9], [10]	
			Communicating between internal services [11]: ① Synchronous message-passing pattern, ② Asynchronous Message-passing pattern, ③ Asynchronous Event-driven pattern	answer [12], [13], [14]	
MDev (40.23%)	Microservice Data Management (8.42%)	Distributed Data Management	Managing data with the combination of event sourcing and CQRS [15]	answer [16], [17]	
			Managing data with single database per microservice (not per instance) [8] [1]	answer [16], [18]	
			Storing data by transaction reliability pattern and processing [15]	answer [19], [20]	
	Communication (25.64%)	Asynchronous Communication	Asynchronous communicating by message-based mechanisms [21]	answer [22], [23]	
			Applying message brokers : Kafka, RabbitMQ and Redis. [24]	answer [25], [26]	
			Communicating with forms [24]: ① Publish and subscribe (Topics) approach ② Point-to-point (Queues) approach	answer [27], [28]	
			Data Formatting	Defining decoder function Defining response, request or header. Using Extra knowledge such as logs	answer [29], [30] answer [31], [32] answer [33], [34]
			Synchronous Communication	Rewriting call method	answer [35], [36]
				Changing parameters. Applying healthy check	answer [37], [38] answer [39], [40]
	Failure Tolerance (6.17%)	Error Handling	Performing resource management	answer [36], [41]	
			Connecting with client-server model	answer [42], [43]	
			Correcting API calls' usage	answer [37], [44]	
MDep (28.89%)	Building (7.67%)	Microservice Project Building [45]	Building with Maven	answer [46], [47]	
			Building with Gradle	answer [48], [49]	
			Adopting popular application framework : Spring framework	answer [50], [51]	
	Deploying (21.22%)	Deployment to Kubernet	Exposing services with Istio [52]	answer [53], [54]	
			Orchestrating services by [8]: ① Kubernetes, ② Docker swarm	answer [55], [56]	
			Docker	Updating version of corresponding components Changing port path Configuring docker composing	answer [57], [58] answer [59], [60] answer [61], [62]
		Spring Application	Changing the details of configuration files	answer [63], [64]	
			Referring to Spring official documentation and GitHub issues	answer [65], [66]	
		Application Hosting	Learning examples from GitHub	answer [67], [68]	
			Referring to official documentation	answer [69], [70]	
			Referring to GitHub examples	answer [71], [72]	
		MG (19.63%)	Service Management (12.52%)	Spring Cloud Netflix	Hosting application by : ① Amazon Web Services (AWS), ② Google Cloud, ③ Microsoft Azure
Referring to Spring official documentation and GitHub issues	answer [76], [77]				
Changing configuration files	answer [78], [79]				
API-Governance	Referring to GitHub examples		answer [80], [81]		
	Referring to GitHub examples		answer [82], [83]		
Microservice Security (7.11%)	Authentication and Authorization		Formatting data style	answer [84], [85]	
			Adopting OAuth and JWT (JSON Web Token) [15]	answer [86], [87]	
			Authenticating with password-based approach	answer [88], [89]	
			Performing security with popular framework [11]: ① Spring cloud gateway, ② Spring security	answer [90], [91]	

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